

QUIZ

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COURSE CODE : ACA-401D

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice ProPlus

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. In which of the following sentence is an example of the wrong use of punctuation?

- In preparation for this review, I purposed and read through each one thoroughly and see how each has generated a concept, find out how they have built their argument and the technique employed in expressing their ideas.¹
- These dissertations display academic writing which read as being defensive, concise, detailed, and bold.
- On the other hand, Fedor (2014) had three chapters, with each having headings.
- The coursepack teaches about different writing styles; technical, commercial or business, journalism, and web copywriting.

¹ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne, C. Booth, Gregory, G. Colomb, Joseph, M. Williams (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 173.

2. **In completing a bibliography, elements are separated by using which punctuation?**
- Comma.
 - Period.²**
 - Semi-colon.
 - Parentheses.
3. **What should a writer do to avoid plagiarism?**
- Use a long quote and place it as a paragraph on its own with quotation marks.
 - Quote all sources used.
 - Use a paraphrase when describing details contained in the source.
 - Cite all sources used.³**
4. **Which of the following is a standard definition of a style guide?**
- A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that needs to be consistent.⁴**
 - The ability to follow a Standard English writing style.
 - The use of correct punctuation, clear grammar and vocabulary.
 - The ability of a writer to follow their prescribed style in preparing any document.

² Turabian, 92.

³ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 5.

⁴ Cleenewerk and Gulma, 24.

5. **In the WHO Style Guide, bibliographies include one of the following functions.**

- The bibliography should provide sufficient information to guide the reader to the source document.
- It provides information on the list of works cited in the main publication.
- A list of unrestricted works cited in the text as sources of data or information.
- They function as a list of references relevant to the subject matter and recommended for further reading, usually not cited in the publication.⁵**

6. **A research report differs from other forms of persuasive writing by all of the following statements except.**

- It describes our opinions, feelings and argues for our beliefs about a topic.⁶**
- It must contain shared facts that readers accept as truths independent of feelings and beliefs.
- Research reports provide readers with reasoning from the evidence they provide to support claims.
- A research report should also show the readers the reasoning behind the findings.

7. **A research argument can be viewed as all but one of the following.**

- A narrative that aims to provide answers to imagined readers' questions.

⁵ World Health Organization, *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004), 5.

⁶ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, ed. Wayne, C. Booth, Gregory, G. Colomb, Joseph, M. Williams (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 173.

- Written down rhetorical strategies that will persuade readers to accept your claim.**⁷
- A narrative that aims to test a claim and support it with evidence.
- A systematic presentation of reasons and evidence for consideration.
8. **Which of the following is a qualitative research method of data collection?**
- Experimentation follows rigid guidelines.
- Uses existing instrumentation.
- The researcher as instrument.**⁸
- Instruments yield performance data, attitude data, and census data.
9. **Which of the following quotes represents the Standard American English?**
- ‘Sally kicked the ball’
- “Sally kicked the ball”
- ‘Sally kicked the ball’.
- “Sally kicked the ball.”**⁹
10. **Within the WHO Style Guide, which of the spelling is normally used?**
- British Spelling.**¹⁰
- American Spelling.

⁷ Turabian, 36.

⁸ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2008), 14.

⁹ Cleenewerck and Gulma, 35.

¹⁰ WHO, 29.

- Concise Oxford dictionary spelling.
- European Commission's English Spelling.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
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